

Comparative study on the geographical, physical and engineering properties of soils of West Bengal. Part-1

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Abstract : Studies on the geographical aspects of West Bengal like land elevation, slope, water courses, river sands, soil colours etc. were made. Three important physical and engineering properties of soils like grain size, free-swell index and permeability of soils from different parts of West Bengal were determined. Usual conclusions were derived from these results.

Keywords : Free-swell index, geographical aspects, grain size, permeability, West Bengal.

The soil exploration is necessary to acquire reliable, specific and detailed information about the soil and ground water condition of the site that may be required for safe economic design. Generally, the extent of soil (below ground level) which may be influenced by the load for the proposed structure is investigated and this zone is termed as the significant depth. The investigation provides the knowledge regarding the occurrence and extent of soil and rock strata, location of ground water. The engineering properties of these sub surface materials can be suitably utilized for construction purposes of different structures like buildings, bridges, dams, roads, railways etc.^{1,2}.

The present investigation is intended to study the geographical aspect of West Bengal and experimentally determine three important physical and engineering properties of soil mainly grain size analysis of different river beds, free swell index and permeability of soils from different parts of West Bengal.

It is known that the soil characteristics of a region or country is related to its geographical nature and the engineering properties on the other hand are very much dependent on soil properties. It is expected that similar geographical conditions may have similar soil and engineering properties though variations are expected due to changes in different physico-chemical and other conditions. Moreover, a gradual variation of the physico-

chemical and engineering properties of soil is likely in different geographical reasons. West Bengal is divided into nine different geographical regions³ which indicate the possibility of gradual variations of soil and engineering properties from the Himalayas to the Bay of Bengal.

The physico-chemical, agronomic and engineering properties of soils from different parts of West Bengal were previously reported⁴⁻⁸.

The object of our present investigation is to conduct a fairly comprehensive studies on the variations of physico-chemical and engineering properties of soil with geographical variations. For this purpose, static and dynamic cone penetration paste, shear test, consolidation test etc. were made. Determination of other parameters like bearing capacity, safe bearing capacity with the nature of soils, porosity, void ratio, Atterberg limits (liquid limit, plastic limit etc.), grain size, permeability, free swell index etc. were also carried out.

The results of our investigation covering the different regions of West Bengal will be described in a series of papers.

The present communication is intended to describe briefly the geographical aspects of West Bengal and show the variation of three important physical and engineering properties of soils (determined experimentally) namely :

- (i) grain size analysis of different river bed materials,
- (ii) free swell index and

(iii) permeability of soils from different parts of West Bengal.

Experimental

Sample collection : Soil samples from different sites and from the desired depths were collected by either direct excavation or boring (diameter of the hole being 100–150 mm in general) by suitable method like auger, wash boring etc. Usually (1' × 1' × 1') box samples were collected after direct excavation. 3–4" diameter, 1–2' or longer undisturbed soil samples were collected by driving samples from boreholes. The samples were sealed with wax to prevent moisture loss and sent to laboratory for testing.

(i) Grain size analysis^{1,2,8} :

The procedure of analysis are :

(a) Sieve analysis (for coarse grained soils only) :

Sieving was performed by arranging the various sieves one over the other in the order of their mesh opening. The largest aperture sieve was kept at the top and the smallest aperture sieve at the bottom over the pan. The assembly containing soil sample on the top sieve was shaken in sieve shaking machine for about ten minutes. The portion of the soil sample retained on each sieve was collected and weighed to calculate the percentage finer in respect of each sieve. Sometimes it was found desirable to wash the sample before use to remove clayey and silt particles. Coarse particles were differentiated by sieving using sieves of appropriate meshes in the usual way^{1,2,9}.

(b) Sedimentation analysis (using hydrometer or pipette) :

The oven dried soil fraction was kept in suspension in a given volume of distilled water. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and the test was started by keeping the jar vertical. The soil particles were assumed to be uniformly distributed throughout the suspension. The analysis was based on Stoke's law assuming the particles to be spherical and the sedimentation velocity was dependent upon the shape, weight and the size of the grain and independent of the nature of particles and the wall of the jar.

The hydrometer gave the density of the soil suspension at the center of the bulb at any time and as the suspension settled, the readings of hydrometer also changed and using a calibration curve the required data for developing the ogive were obtained. In pipette method, a portion of the suspension was withdrawn from a specific depth of the suspension after some specified time vis-à-vis the water temperature and dried to get the weight.

The particle size distribution curve (which gave an

idea about the type and gradation of soil) was obtained by plotting the "percentage finer than" as the ordinate and the particle diameter as the abscissa (on a semi-logarithmic scale).

(ii) Determination of differential free swell index of soils^{1,9} :

Free swell is the increase in volume of a soil without any external constraint, on submergence in water. The index is an indicator of the expansiveness of a particular soil. The expansive soils may cause damage to structures due to shrink-swell activities (with loss and gain of moisture). On the basis of this test, other tests like swelling pressure test etc. are done to assess the destructive power of that soil and precaution is taken accordingly. Differential free swell test is a modified free swell test (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Differential free swell.

Two 10 g specimens of oven dried soil passing 0.42/0.425 mm sieve were taken and poured in two graduated glass cylinders of 100 cc capacity. One cylinder was then filled with a non-polar liquid ((kerosene, generally) and the other with distilled water upto 100 cc. Glass rod was inserted and stirred to remove entrapped air. Soils in both the cylinders were left to settle for 24 h to attain equilibrium. The final volume of soils in each cylinder was read.

Fig. 2. Constant head permeability test set up.

(iii) Permeability test :

Two laboratory methods are used viz. the constant

head test and the variable head test. Both the tests can be done on any type of soil, but generally, constant head permeability test is carried out on coarse grained soils in which a reasonable discharge can be collected in a given time. The falling head permeability test is done on relatively less permeable soils in which discharge is small. However, in the present work the results of the constant head permeability test had been given, though many the soil samples were cohesive.

An aspirator bottle was used as the reservoir having a standpipe running through it. The pipe was the passage of air intake as the water permeated through the soil specimen, in such a way that at the outlet point of the bottle the pressure was always zero. The hydraulic head, applied by placing the soil specimen at some depth with respect to the bottle always remained constant (Fig. 2).

The soil specimen in the mould was of diameter 3" (76.2 mm) and length 1' (25.4 mm). As the sample got saturated and water started to come through it, discharge was taken and measured at a time interval.

Fig. 3. Different geographical regions of West Bengal.

Results

(1) Grain size^{1,29} :

Mean diameters or mean weight diameters were obtained from the particle size distribution curves of the soils. The results are given in Table 1. The grain size distribution curves of some river sands of West Bengal is presented in Fig. 4.

(2) Differential free-swell index ($S_d\%$)⁹ :

$$S_d \% = \frac{V_d - V_k}{V_k} \times 100 \tag{1}$$

where V_d = volume of specimen in cylinder with water and V_k = volume of specimen in cylinder with kerosene.

The degree of expansion can be known from Table 2.

Mean diameter (D_m , mm) of Karru sand
 $= 1/3 (D_{85} + D_{50} + D_{15})$
 $= 1/3 (1.7 + 0.62 + 0.34) = 0.890 \text{ mm}$

- Barang — Coarse to medium sand; white with bluish tinge
- Karru — Well graded gravelly coarse sand; brownish yellow
- Kangsabati — Coarse to medium sand; brownish yellow
- Hooghly — Uniform medium sand; grey
- Digha sea beach — Uniform fine sand; yellow with brownish tinge

Fig. 4. Grain size distribution curves of different river sand of West Bengal.

(3) Permeability^{10,11}

Permeability or hydraulic conductivity is the measure

Table 1. List of typical sample of bed/bank toe materials of different rivers/water courses of West Bengal

River	Place	Geographical region	Mean diameter (D_m , mm) Mean dia. (D_m , mm) $= \frac{D_{85} + D_{50} + D_{15}}{3}$
Raidak	Bhutan Ghat	2	13.490
Torsa	Hāsimara	2	0.550
Kaljani	Cooch Behar	3	0.223
Karatowa	Jalpaiguri	2-3	0.260
Teesta	Confluence of River Dharla	2-3	0.566
Teesta	Barnes	2-3	0.295
Mahananda	Siliguri	2-3	0.660
Barang	Chopra	3	0.370
Dauk	Barrage site, North Dinajpur	3	0.370
Kangsaboti	Teledi, Purulia	4	0.580
Karru	Baghmundi, Purulia	4	0.890
Dwarakeswar	Bankura	5	1.218
Dwarka	Barrage site, Birbhum	5	1.093
Mayurakshi	Mossanjore, Birbhum	5	0.593
Kopai	Barrage site	5	0.694
Ajoy	Ilambazar, Birbhum	5	0.471
Damodar	Durgapur Barrage	5	0.523
Kangsaboti	Kankab ti Ghat, Medinipur	5	0.760
Kana Damodar	Hooghly	6	0.440
Rupnarayan	Kolaghat, Medinipur	6	0.183
Ganga	Farakka Barrage	6	0.164
Padma	Akhriganj, Murshidabad	6	0.135
Bhagirathi	Berhampur	6	0.231
Bhagirathi	Prachin Mayapur, Nadia	6	0.125
Hooghly	Kalna, Bardhaman	6	0.183
Hooghly	Palta, 24-Parganas (N)	6	0.139
Hooghly	Sukhchar, 24-Parganas (N)	6	0.178
Haroagong	Boalghata, 24-Parganas (N)	6	0.125
Kalindi	Tentulia	7	0.130
Hooghly	Nayachara Island, Haldia, Medinipur	6	0.096
Mridanga Bhanga	24-Parganas (S)	7	0.135
Sea	Digha Sea Beach, Medinipur	8	0.125

The values of D_{85} , D_{50} , D_{15} are obtained from the particle size distribution curve of the particular sand/gravelly sand

of the ability of soil (or a porous material), which permits the conduction of water through its interconnecting voids to conduct water.

Permeability has enormous influence on other engineering properties of the sub-soils. It also controls the transport of water soluble chemicals through the soils.

Following Darcy's law, the coefficient of permeability or the saturated hydraulic conductivity K is given

$$K = \frac{Q.L}{h.t.A} \quad (2)$$

where K = coefficient of permeability or Darcy's constant. It is defined as the average velocity of flow that will occur through the total cross-sectional area of the soil under unit hydraulic gradient (expressed as cm/s or m/day), A = total cross-sectional area of the soil mass, h = hydraulic head applied, L = length or thickness of the sample.

From eq. (2), K is obtained. Temperature of water is

Table 2. Some typical values of the differential free swell index of soils of different places of West Bengal

Soil sample	District	Geographical region	%SD	Degree of expansion
Kaoline	—	—	0	Low
Bentonite	—	—	205	Very high
Islampur soil (Low-lying)	Dinajpur (N)	3	0	Low
Maldah soil (Low-lying)	Maldah		3	0 Low
Boalghata soil	24-Parganas (S)	7	0	Low
Nadia clay	Nadia	6	0	Low
Kolkata clay	Kolkata	6	4	Low
Uluberia clay	Haora	6	6	Low
Bankura clay	Bankura	4-5	26	Moderate
Purulia clay	Purulia	4	20	Low to moderate
Bamunda clay	Medinipur (W)	5	44	High
Rondia clay	Bardhaman	5-6	43	High
Namkhana clay	24-Parganas (S)	7	67	Very high
Pathar Pratima clay	24-Parganas (S)	7	15	Low

% SD : Degree of expansion
 <20 : Low
 20-35 : Moderate
 35-50 : High
 >50 : Very high

taken during the test and a correction factor is applied to get K_{27} at 27 °C. The permeability is a function of grain size, clay content, void ratio, arrangement of soil pores, degree of saturation, the properties of pore fluid etc. The permeability of some typical soils are given in Table 3.

Discussion

(a) Geography of the region under study :

The lower Ganga plain (apparently a homogeneous geographical entity), the Himalayan fringe in the north and the Purulia uplands (an extension of the Ranchi plateau), in the west from the state of West Bengal. There are some micro-order diversities that bring out different physico-graphic subdivisions comprising nineteen districts. The state may be divided into the following geographical regions⁶ (Fig. 3).

- (1) Darjeeling and the Himalayan Mountains
- (2) The Terrain Region
- (3) Northern Plains : (a) Duars, (b) Barind tract
- (4) The Rolling Uplands and Plateau scraps in the West
- (5) The Rarh
- (6) The Ganga Delta : (a) Moribund Delta (Murshidabad, Nadia), (b) Mature Delta (Haora, Hooghly, parts of Bardhaman, Birbhum, Medinipur), (c) Active Delta [North and South 24-Parganas, Kolkata, Medinipur (East)]
- (7) The Sunderb ns
- (8) The Sandy coastal plains

(i) Land elevation, slope and meteorology :

The Northern and Western borders encompass areas slightly or well above 100 m from mean sea level, while more than two-thirds of surface have an elevation within 30 m. Average land elevation of the region south of the city of Kolkata (Calcutta) is below 6 m. In the North the land slope is southwardly and in the south the general land slope of the lower Ganga plain as revealed by the drainage/river system is towards south-east to south. The delta proper has a land gradient of less than 2 cm per kilometer, while the areas in the immediate vicinity show gradients upto 40 cm per kilometer. Only a narrow strip along the northern border of the state exhibits slope in the order of 100 cm per kilometer.

The north is colder and the annual rainfall is more than 300 cm. The annual rainfall is 150-200 cm in the south and 125-150 cm in the west^{3,12}.

(ii) Water courses :

The Ganga is the main river of the state. It enters West Bengal in Malda district and near Nurpur in Murshidabad it gets bifurcated. The main branch, the Padma, enters Bangladesh and the other branch, the Bhagirathi, traverses a length of 520 km before falling in

to the Bay of Bengal, south of the Sagar Island. The tidal effect is observed in the stretch of 290 km from Sagar to Swarupnagar, Nadia and this reach is known as the Hooghly river¹³.

In the North, high land slope and heavy rainfall make the rivers flow rapidly during and after heavy rains. The

Table 3. Some typical permeability coefficient (K) values of soils of different places of West Bengal

Sample no.	District	Region	% of fines (silt + clay)	% of clay	K (cm/s)
Pha-1	Darjeeling	2	5.5	0	9.4×10^{-3}
Pha-2	Do	2	73.0	4.4	1.8×10^{-6}
Pha-3	Do	2	3.0	0	1.0×10^{-2}
Ria-1	Dinajpur (N)	3	19.8	3.7	3.0×10^{-5}
Raj-1	Bardhaman	5	89.5	42.2	3.1×10^{-6}
Mon-1	Birbhum	6	16.3	5.6	2.3×10^{-4}
Aus-1	Bardhaman	6	58.5	11.1	3.0×10^{-5}
Bha-1	Medinipur (W)	6	88.0	46.8	3.3×10^{-7}
Amt-1	Haora	6	89.0	23.4	2.4×10^{-7}
Anj-1	Nadia	6	98.0	36.8	4×10^{-7}
Kar-1	Do	6	52.5	3.6	5.3×10^{-5}
Mat-1	Do	6	15.0	1.1	9.5×10^{-4}
Kha-1	24-Parganas (N)	6	99.4	63.5	3.3×10^{-7}
Pag-1	Do	6	39.3	1.6	6.9×10^{-4}
Bag-1	Kolkata	6	97.0	18.2	5.9×10^{-8}
Jag-1	24-Parganas (N)	6-7	98.9	35.8	
Jag-3	Do	6-7	13.0	0	
Bas-1	24-Parganas (S)	7	90.5	15.5	
Bas-2	Do	7	86.0	29.8	
Bas-4	Do	7	70.0	9.4	
Jha-2	Do	7	92.0	11.4	
Dho-3	Do	6-7	35.0	2.1	
Dho-4	Do	6-7	3.0	0	
Dia-1	Do	6	91.0	34.2	10^{-8}
Dia-2	Do	6	94.8	40.9	$\times 10^{-8}$
Dia-4	Do	6	89.9	29.8	1.6×10^{-7}
Ten-3	Do	6-7	84.4	16.3	9.3×10^{-7}
Ten-4	Do	6-7	77.4	10.9	5×10^{-6}
Ten-6	Do	6-7	7.2	0	9.5×10^{-4}
Raj-1	Do	7	97.0	31.3	3×10^{-7}
Shi-1	Do	7	98.0	38.9	1.1×10^{-6}
Shi-2	Do	7	99.0	38.2	2.8×10^{-7}
Dig-1	Medinipur (E)	8	0	0	2.2×10^{-2}
Dig-3	Do	8	65.6	1.6	4.5×10^{-3}

$K > 10^{-4}$ cm/s – permeable – (sand or sand with very little fines)

$K = 10^{-4}$ to 10^{-7} cm/s – semi permeable – (sand/silt with some clay)

$K < 10^{-7}$ cm/s impermeable – (clay)

river beds are formed of gravel and sand and the carrying capacity of the rivers is poor. Rapid course shift of the rivers and devastating floods are regular phenomena in the region. The rivers are the Teesta, Torsa, Karatoa, Mahananda, Jaldhaka, Kaljani, Dharala, Raidak etc. The rivers ultimately join the Padma Brahmaputra system in Bangladesh¹².

The rivers of the west flow in the south east direction. The Dwarka, Brahmani, Mayurakshi, Ajoy, Damodar, Silabati, Kangsabati, Rupnarayan, Kaliaghai etc. drain into the Bhagirathi-Hooghly river. Only the Subarnarekha falls directly into the Bay of Bengal. The eastern tributaries of Bhagirathi-Hooghly are the Churni, Jalangi etc. which are basically the spill channels of the Padma. The Ganga and some of the rivers of the north are partially snow-fed. These rivers and other rivers flow mainly in low stream and run in torrents in the monsoon months only.

Some areas in the Rarh and western margin of the Ganga Delta are low-lying. In the peak of the monsoon (August-September) high flow in the rivers and the drainage congestion created by the high tide in the estuary lead to inundation of some areas of Bardhaman, Hooghly, Haora and Medinipur (East)¹². In the east, some low-lying areas of Nadia are susceptible to flood. Poor land slope, poor carrying capacity of the choked up drainage channels and tidal lockage created in different creeks in the south, cause the city of Kolkata and many low-lying areas in southern region (North and South 24-Parganas) to get flooded often in the monsoon period.

(b) River sands :

The Table 1 shows the list of the mean diameter of bed material of different rivers of West Bengal and the Fig. 4 gives the particle size distribution curves of some of the sands. The mean diameter of a sand is the average value of the diameters corresponding to 85, 50 and 15% finer, which are obtained from the particle/grain size distribution curve of the sand. The value of mean diameter is used in estimating the scour depth required in the design of a bridge foundation and river protection works¹.

The variation of sand sizes at different places of different regions is self-interpreting, generally more a river is near to the sea, less is the sand size. It is obvious that the bed materials of the rivers are finer in size from north towards south and from west towards east-southeast. Basically, this is function of the stage of the river, land slope, velocity and discharge etc. Of course, the data presented here are typical values. Higher values in the upper regions do not mean that finer materials are not

available there. The values are, in general, the representative ones at those sites. In the lower regions, however, coarser soils are not at all available. For this reason good coarse materials of civil engineering use are brought from Cooch Behar, Jalpaiguri, North Dinajpur in the north and Birbhum, Bankura, Bardhaman, Medinipur (West), Hooghly in the south.

(c) Soil colour :

The earth crust is composed of eight elements viz. oxygen (41.3%), silicon (27.7%), aluminium (9.8%) and iron (4.5%) etc. of which compounds of iron present in the rock minerals in the form of oxides, carbonates, sulphides etc. contribute mainly to the colour of the resultant soils. However, darkness in colour is caused by the organic matters.

Unhydrated ferric oxides impart reddish/brownish colour, but yellowish colour may appear by hydration. Reddish colour is indicative of good drainage and oxidising condition; while bluish tinge is created by reducing condition prevalent in poorly drained tracts. Mottling in soil is resulted due to alternating oxidising and reducing condition in the past^{14,15}.

The colour of the soils of different regions of West Bengal clearly indicates the chemical environments prevalent during the formation. The colour of the soils of the north and west indicate that the regions are better drained having fluctuating ground water table and the oxidizing environment is prevalent in the soil system of the upper horizon while the reducing environment is prevalent in the poorly drained south having high ground water table.

(d) Particle size :

Particle size is a primary physical property and depending on grain size, soil classification according to Indian Standard Classification is :

		0.002 mm	0.75 mm	0.425 mm	2.0 mm	4.75 mm	20 mm	80 mm	300 mm		
Clay	Silt	Fine	Medium	Coarse	Fine	Coarse			Cobble	Boulder	
		Sand			Gravel						

Clay sized fraction is heavy and have poor drainage and aeration capability. Silts are combinations of clay minerals like hydrous Fe- and Al-oxides. They are fine materials with large surface area, have good absorption and exchanges capabilities. They are highly productive for plant medium. Sands are light, have drainage capability (but poor in water retention), chemically rather inert. They are poor sources or nutrients but can be readily aerated.

(e) *Differential free swell index* :

The differential free swell indices indicate the capacity of expansion of a soil. The degree of expansion depends on the following factors : (i) mineralogy, (ii) clay content, (iii) salt concentration, (iv) salt variety (ionic charges of ions).

Water is a polar liquid while kerosene is non-polar. In the expanding lattice of a clay mineral, the entry of water causes volume increase. So, more the specific surface of the soil is, more is the chance of expansion. Secondly, salt concentration causes lowering of the double layer thickness and increase in flocculation. The result of the present study given in the Table 2 may be interpreted in the following way^{1,9}.

Kaolinite (1 : 1 clay) shows poor activity due to low surface area and bentonite (a mineral of montmorillonite group, 2 : 1 clay) has high activity and high specific surface. So, expansivity of bentonite is very high and that of kaolinite is very low, practically nil.

Islampur soil is silty, Maldah soil is a mixture of sand and silt and Boalghata soil is sand. Lack of clay in these soils is the cause of very low expansivity. It corroborates the fact that expansion is a clay phenomenon. Similarly, lack of clay in the Uluberia soil is the main cause of low expansion. Kolkata and Nadia clay have medium clay content values and the predominating mineral is illite. Both the soils have shown poor expansivity. Both the Bankura and Purulia soils are composed mainly of clays of kaolinite group. But the soils have shown rather medium values regarding expansion. Bamunda (near Bhasraghat) and Rondia clays are old alluvium and these are expansive soils. These expectedly have shown high differential free swell values.

The Namkhana clay is silty clay and contains high salt concentration. It forms very high flocculated structure when allowed to settle in water. However, the Patharpratima soil contains low clay percentage and in spite of high salt content it has not shown much expansion.

(f) *Permeability* :

The permeability coefficient of a soil mass is utilized to assess or predict the discharge through it. A soil material chosen in the dam construction should be of low permeability to reduce seepage loss. Conversely during placement of tube well such an aquifer is searched that may yield sufficient water i.e. coarse grain is preferable. In general, more the clay content of soils, the lesser is the permeability. The permeability is low if silt and clay content is above 85% in general.

In an alluvial tract, the type reveals the geological past of the site. Coarse materials are borne along a river course and finer soils settle on the flood plains. A sequential change of layers (i.e. alternate clay and sand) at a particular place depicts regular course shift of the river in the geological past. In the western districts of West Bengal lateritic and old alluvium are encountered, soils are reddish brown or yellowish in colour. In the north Terai, whitish soils and sandy alluvium are found. The more one moves towards south, finer the soils (generally silty clay) he will face. In the south the soils are grey, dark grey and sometimes blackish due to presence of decomposed organic matter.

Due to very low landscape the southern region is not free draining, another cause is flow tide. The ground water is high, near to ground level and the intense cultivation procedure is followed in this densely populated region. As a whole a reductive environment is enforced on the sub-soils, which is to some extent man made.

There are many sandy patches of top soils in Hooghly, Murshidabad, Nadia and North 24-Parganas. These, along with the sandy soils of the river banks are the potential sources through which the ground water of the southern region is replenished, particularly during the monsoon month.

Due to intense cultivation ground water is imprudently being exploited in the region. The result is the crisis of ground water, lowering of water table in the lean period (summer), at the same time due to destabilization of geochemical status of the ground water, the quality of ground water is gradually deteriorating.

It is apparent that the permeability values are high in Northern part (Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri, Dinajpur) and western part (Purulia, Bankura, Birbhum, Medinipur (East and West except a small fringe areas) indicating easy recharging of the aquifers. Moreover good draining facilities, oxidative condition prevails. These together with laterite soil make water rather free from 'As'.

Conversely, in South and North 24-Parganas, Nadia, Murshidabad and Malda, the alluvial soils have high clay and fine contents. The permeability values are low, aquifers are likely to be poorly recharged. The poor draining capability caused the anoxic condition to prevail. Thus, proper replenishment of the aquifers is a remote possibility particularly due to heavy withdrawal of water for Boro cultivation and 'As' contamination in water is high. However these are some possible reasons among other numerous possibilities.

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